

Results of the 2024 Season of the Sikait Project: Excavation and Survey of Middle Sikait, Documentation of the Emerald Mines, and Survey of the Wadi el-Gemal National Park

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Abstract: Results of the 2024 Season of the Sikait Project

The 2024 season of the Sikait Project has deepened our knowledge of the features and evolution of the area known to classical authors as the “Smaragdos”, the main source of green beryl within the Roman Empire. The work focused on the survey and excavation in Middle Sikait, the documentation of the emerald mines, and the conservation interventions in the site of Sikait.

Introduction

During January and February 2024, the Sikait Project team continued various archaeological activities in the Wadi el-Gemal National Park, primarily focusing on the Wadi Sikait area.¹ This season’s work centered on the Middle Sikait area, where the team conducted an intensive survey and excavated one of the buildings. Additionally, the project continued documenting the emerald mines of Wadi Sikait, including not only the topography of some of the most remarkable mines but also the excavation of several trenches both inside and outside the mines. As in the previous season, the team also carried out a topographic survey of two endangered sites in the region, Zabara and Ibayd. Finally, the conservation team continued its work on the preservation of archaeological structures and materials.

Wadi Sikait is in the Eastern Desert, on a branch tributary of Wadi Gemal, 45 km inland from the Red Sea coast. It is one of the main areas of occurrence of beryl within the Wadi el-Gemal National Park, a region known in ancient literary authors as the “Smaragdos”, because it was the only one in the Roman Empire where

emeralds could be extracted (Pl. I 1).² Since the Ptolemaic period but especially after the Roman conquest of Egypt, an intense extraction process of beryl started in this area, with the creation of an extensive network of mining settlements (Pl. I 2), the most remarkable of these being the site at Sikait: a settlement cut into two parts – an eastern and a western one – by the Wadi Sikait, extending 560 m north-south by 270 m east-west. Chronologically, it lies between the 1st and the 7th-8th centuries AD.

The work in this area was started by the team directed by S.E. Sidebotham from the University of Delaware in the 1990s and early 2000s. The Sikait Project is a joint archaeological mission between the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona and the Polish Centre of Mediterranean Archaeology that resumed this previous surveying and excavation work.³ The primary aim of the project is to analyze the extraction and commercialization of beryl – a mineral whose green variant is better known as emerald – during the Graeco-Roman period in Egypt. The present paper offers an overview of the results of the 2024 season.

The excavation in Wadi Sikait

Sikait is an ancient site situated within the Wadi el-Gemal National Park, in the southern region of Wadi Sikait, a tributary of the Wadi Gemal. Its coordinates are UTM 36N 681788E 2725330N.⁴ It is the largest settlement in the region, containing 150 to 200 structures, including

All maps, plans and photographs for which no other source is given are by the authors.

1 We would like to thank the Egyptian authorities from the Supreme Council of Antiquities for granting the permits for the 2024 season, especially inspectors, Mr. Mohamed Mubarak and Mr. Mohamed Azizy. The project also extends its gratitude to Mr. Abdelrahim Mahmoud Ahmed, Director of the SCA Red Sea Inspectorate, and Mr. Mahmoud Ahmed Hussein, Director of Excavations and Missions in the Red Sea area. We would also like to thank the management of the National Park of Wadi el-Gemal and the rest of the Egyptian staff for ensuring the correct working of the season. The work was funded by the Fundación PALARQ and several private donors, among which we must highlight Arqueòlegs.cat. Pottery research in this study was conducted as part of Preludium21 grant titled “Sail South to Reach the East - Berenike and Red Sea as a Lacking Puzzle of Late Antique Indian Ocean Trade”, funded by the National Science Centre (2022/45/N/HS3/01784).

2 For these references in the classical authors, see Oller 2022.

3 Regarding the previous archaeological seasons at Sikait, see Rivard – Foster – Sidebotham 2002; Sidebotham et al. 2004; Foster et al. 2007, 304-343; Sidebotham – Hense – Nouwens 2008, 328-336; Sidebotham 2011; Oller et al. 2019; Sidebotham – Gates-Foster – Rivard 2019, 136-145; Oller et al. 2021a; Oller et al. 2021b; García-Dils et al. 2021; Oller et al. 2022a; Oller et al. 2023.

4 All UTM coordinates are referenced to the WGS84 datum.

at least four temples and extensive emerald mining areas.

The primary objective for the season was to continue excavating the site. This year, the team expanded their focus to an area known as Middle Sikait (SKMZ-H), located approximately 2 km north in the Wadi Sikait (Pl. II). Several years ago, an extensive mining area was identified at this location,⁵ around the coordinates UTM 36N 682657E 2728156N. Its importance is clear from the large amount of mining debris present in the area, mainly coming from open-air extraction operations, but also with some galleries and shafts. Particularly interesting is the mine SKPUS-125, located some 500 m from the Middle Sikait site and already documented in previous seasons.⁶ In this mine we documented a corpus of ancient graffiti, including two graffiti of the legio III Cyrenaica, that attested the direct involvement of the Roman army in the exploitation of the area.⁷ This aspect should be seen together with the presence of a large stone ramp connecting the wadi with the mining zone, the existence of different impressive buildings, and of two massive watchtowers on the surrounding hills. Altogether, these elements suggested the importance of the area and the need to do some work on it. This work involved an intensive survey and the excavation of one of the buildings.

As for the survey, it covered all the way from Wadi Sikait to the location of Middle Sikait (Pl. III 1). The goal was to determine the chronology of the large amount of pottery existent in this area and, if possible, suggest an explanation of this concentration of material. A team of six archaeologists covered the entire area, selecting only diagnostic material. The results have been extremely interesting, as most of these materials belong to the Early Roman period, between the end of the 1st c. BC to the beginning of the 2nd c. AD.⁸ Apart from that, an important number of imported materials were found, including wine amphorae and oil containers from all over the Mediterranean. The features of these materials may suggest that they were related to the presence of the Roman army in this space, probably in a non-permanent camp at the base of the wadi, with easy access to the mines. The recovery of common wares, as cooking pots, casseroles, and mortaria, may reinforce this hypothesis.

Regarding the excavation, a trench (Trench 025) was opened in the buildings located at the top of the mining area, just after the end of the stone ramp coming from the wadi. Three of these buildings were built on the same artificial terrace and with the same constructive pattern: a large rectangular building composed of

three rooms, the first of which is the largest, the second somewhat smaller, and the third one of niche-type and partially rock-cut (Pl. III 2). This same pattern was found also in other areas such as the main settlement in Sikait, Nugrus, Gali, or Kab Marfu'a. They have been usually interpreted as temples and, therefore, the team decided to open a trench in the two last rooms of the first building, preliminary named "Temple A" (Pl. IV 1).

The excavation focused on the second and third room. The first room – 6.24 m of width by 6.32 m of length – was not excavated. It contains the main entrance, preceded by three stone steps. The second room could be accessed through a small door – 1.05 m of width – flanked by masonry walls. Its dimensions are 2.63 of width by 3.57 m of length and a maximum preserved height of 2.12 m. Finally, the third chamber is at a higher level, 1 m above the floor of the second room. In fact, it is more similar to a large niche than to an actual room and it is partially rock-cut and partially built with masonry walls, with dimensions of 1.49 m of length, 2.92 m of width and a maximum preserved height of 1.26 m.

During the excavation of the two spaces several tumble levels came to light covering the last circulation layer associated with the use of the possible temple. These levels were related with the tumble of the ceiling and walls of the rooms. Upon them, an interesting lead medallion was found depicting an image of the god Harpocrates (Pl. IV 2). In the niche, the bedrock appeared under the tumble. However, the second room offered a more complicated stratigraphy. There, under the last layer of tumble, a new locus appeared that already offered a slight change. It was composed mainly of brownish sand with just a few stones but having many pottery sherds on it. It corresponded to the abandonment level of the temple. It is followed by a more compacted layer of brownish earth with abundant remains of mortar, probably the last level of use in the temple. After the excavation of it, the original floor of the room was discovered. Basically, the bedrock was used by regularizing it with the use of some type of plaster that was also found covering the lower part of the room's walls. Over the plaster-floor we recovered another important finding: a small terracotta figurine of a Sothic dog (Pl. IV 3).

The most interesting part of the original circulation level is that it contains two votive pits: the first one is circular and lies in the middle of the room (Pl. V 1). Inside of it appeared several votive offerings, consisting of different steatite dishes with some organic residues on it, burned beads, seeds, a pendant with the representation of the god Min on its lower part, a large, burned shell, and a small steatite figurine of a horned altar (Pl. V 2). Attached to the wall flanking the entrance to the second room, an L-shaped offering pit was excavated, inside of which were two large faience beads. Beside this pit, a rectangular copper alloy plaque was recovered (Pl. VI 1). This last material is particularly intriguing, as it

5 Sidebotham et al. 2019, 146-153.

6 For the features of this mine, see Oller et al. 2021b, 32-33; García-Dils et al. 2021, 40-43.

7 Regarding these graffiti, see García Dils et al. 2022.

8 However, some recovered materials – fragments of Knidian, Koan, and Rhodian amphora – confirmed the existence of a Late Ptolemaic phase in the area – 1st c. BC.

presents an inscription that remains under investigation. Moreover, it features the symbol of the goddess Tanit. This element, along with the horned altar, may suggest a potential “Semitic connection” for this site that needs to be further investigated.

Thus, the position, architectural features, and recovered materials of the two rooms confirmed that we are dealing, most likely, with a religious building complex related to the mining operations. This is reinforced by the presence of a massive stone structure composed of a large rectangular base with a square feature on top of it just in front of “Temple A”. Although the structure is severely damaged, its position and features suggest that it is some kind of altar, as it is similar to – but larger than – other ones found in the mining roads around the area (Pl. VI 2). In the following seasons, a cleaning of the tumble will be conducted in order to better understand this structure and its function.

The analysis of the pottery found in the last use level of the temple together with one coin,⁹ suggests a chronological span between the end of the 1st c BC to the beginning of the 2nd c. AD, fitting perfectly with the chronology of the activities in the Middle Sikait area survey. Further seasons will focus on the excavation of the first room of the Temple A, and the other two possible temples of Middle Sikait (Pl. VII 1).

The survey and documentation of the emerald mines

A significant objective of this season was to advance the geological and archaeological documentation of the settlement’s surrounding area, with particular emphasis on the extraction zones.¹⁰ New mining areas were identified, including several sites in North Sikait, where a new zone, SKMZ-T, covering 2.8 ha, was defined. Concurrently, the initiation of a survey in the Nugrus area led to the creation of SKMZ-S, a new area spanning 0.5 ha.

Archaeologically, the focus was primarily on SKMZ-G, the largest extraction area discovered to date. The documented area of this zone expanded to 24 ha, encompassing 196 underground structures, 189 of which are extraction sites. Exploration efforts concentrated on the Underground Complex SKPUS-229-230-231-232-426, named according to the codes assigned to its five known entrances. This complex represents the largest subterranean exploitation recorded thus far, consisting of numerous galleries, with a surveyed length exceeding 600 m and a depth of

-48.05 m. Its usage spans a timeframe from the Early Roman period to the Early Umayyad period.

This year, a comprehensive survey of the subterranean complex was conducted using a high-precision topographic device (Pl. VII 2). As a result, the mine was almost fully documented, revealing over 600 m of galleries and at least five entrances. One of the most significant discoveries of the project to date was made in this mine: a pair of slate tablets used as tags for transporting baskets of emeralds from within the mine (Pl. VIII 1). Both tags bear inscriptions referencing the cohorts Nigri Camerensiana, a Roman military unit previously known from an ostrakon linking it to the Wadi el-Gemal fort. The discovery of these inscriptions deep within the mine reinforces the hypothesis of direct Roman military involvement in mining operations. Moreover, it suggests that extraction activities in this area may have commenced as early as the reign of Emperor Tiberius, ca. 15-18 AD. Finally, the find potentially clarifies the origin of the name “Wadi Nugrus”, located nearby, which may be connected to the presence of the cohorts Nigri Camerensiana, referred to as “Nígrou” (Νίγρου) in the tags.

Additionally, three small trenches were excavated in SKMZ-G to gather further information on ancient extraction operations. The first, Trench 022, was placed outside the mine SKPUS229 in a “sorting area”, a space used for the initial processing of the extracted crystals (Pl. VIII 2). The trench, measuring 1 m N/S by 6 m W/E, was positioned across the central part of this zone. Although the excavation yielded limited material –some pottery fragments and pieces of beryl – it significantly enhanced the understanding of the processing system. The findings suggest that several workers were involved in handling the extracted mineral, with the central part of the sorting area used to separate beryl from waste, which was then accumulated around the perimeter, forming a circular space. Pottery yielded 1st to 2nd c. AD dating of this working space. High percentage of kitchen and utility wares indicates that this area served also as food preparation or/and consumption place.

A second trench was excavated inside of mine 229, particularly in the chamber where the inscribed labels appeared, to recover other interesting materials related to the extraction process. Trench 023 involved the excavation of this chamber, in a space of 2 by 2 m that communicates with several galleries and shafts (Pl. IX 1). There, only one level of sediment was found, coming from the mining waste. After removing 50 cm of this sediment, the original floor of the chamber was reached. Most of the material recovered was of organic type, basically textiles, including several fragments of rope, strings, and an almost complete bag, probably used for extracting the emeralds coming from the mine (Pl. IX 2).

Finally, the third trench, Trench 024, was conducted in an underground structure inside of the mining zone G. Last year, a large amount of imported pottery

9 The dating of this copper-alloy obol, minted in Alexandria, should be assigned to the period between 17 and 20 AD. See RPC I 5075, RPC I 5082, RPC I 5087.

10 Regarding the previous work conducted in the area from a geological point of view, see: Hassan and El-Shatoury 1976; Shaw et al. 1999; Harrell 2004; Harrell 2006; Grundmann and Morteani 2008; Abu el-Enen et al. 2016; Harrell 2019; Ali et al. 2021; Abdalla and Saleh 2021; Gilg and Grundmann 2022; Harrell 2024; Zaki Kehdr et al. 2024.

was recovered in front of this feature, suggesting a storage space from the beginning of the exploitation of the mines, in the early 1st c. AD. The structure was perfectly carved in the bedrock, with a maximum height of 1 m and a depth of some 10 m (Pl. X 1). A stone wall flanking the southern part of the entrance was added at some point, reducing its dimensions, while a pair of small cavities was carved at the northern and western edges of the underground structure.

The excavation documented a thick layer of sediment composed of windblown sand and debris coming from the bedrock excavation, arriving at some points at 60 cm of depth. Unfortunately, only a few fragments of pottery were recovered from inside this structure. Thus, it was not possible to confirm the hypothesis of a storage space. However, the presence of modern matches inside of it suggests that this space was looted at some point between the 19th and 20th century. Due to this fact, together with the recovery of the pottery sherds in front of the structure, the use as storage space cannot be excluded. The material is dominated by amphorae – 89% of total assemblage – and is showing a spectacularly high contribution of Mediterranean imports – 19.6% of the total amphorae assemblage.¹¹ The geographical range of encountered containers spans from the Black Sea (Heraclea Pontica) to the Central-West Mediterranean (Mauretania). Additionally, a rim of a south Indian storage jar was found, whose origin has been confirmed by petrographic analysis.

The finds in this space are similar to the material recovered during the survey of Middle Sikait. The important percentage of Mediterranean imports, together with a chronology that starts – at least – at the beginning of the Early Roman period, suggest that both Middle Sikait and the SKMZ-G were two of the first beryl-bearing areas intensively exploited by the Roman Empire, probably starting under the reign of Augustus/Tiberius. The initial mining operations were directly related to the Roman army, as is shown by the important epigraphic evidence found in both areas. The fact that there was a legion in Middle Sikait and a cohort in zone G poses the question whether there was any type of hierarchical relationship between both army units – with the cohort depending on the legion – or whether they were operating independently and the extracting processes were divided between them. Further evidence coming from the mining areas will hopefully provide answers to these questions.

Finally, we conducted some survey of the pathways connecting this area. It is evident that this zone was transformed to facilitate the movement of people and goods since the beginning of the large-scale mining operations. Thus, for instance, several paths were

adapted to communicate with areas such as Wadi Sikait and Wadi Nugrus. During the 2024 season, one of these paths was surveyed, particularly a secondary wadi that connects the beginning of the mining zone with Wadi Nugrus. Known as the Wadi Umm Selimate, it is probably the first spot where the Roman army started to look for mineral veins, as it shows the same ceramic materials as found in the underground structures documented there, for example in the previously mentioned possible warehouse excavated in trench 024.¹²

One of the most impressive structures documented in this small wadi is a stone bridge placed in front of a waterfall that was used to avoid a detour through the mountain because of the over 10 m of fall at this spot that prevents a direct trail through the wadi (Pl. X 3).¹³ The structure is leaning on the bedrock and has some 4 m of height by 7 m of preserved length and 1.5 m of width. It is astonishingly well preserved – except for the part directly standing over the waterfall, which is destroyed by the water. It is covered by large schist slabs and allowed to walk easily from the waterfall to its surface. After crossing the bridge, one can take a pathway smoothly going down on the eastern slope until recovering the base of the wadi.

The survey of the Wadi el-Gemal National Park

One of the main goals of this season was to continue the survey of several archaeological sites within the Wadi el-Gemal National Park that are severely endangered, especially by the activities of illegal gold diggers using heavy machinery and metal detectors. Thanks to the permits granted by the Supreme Council of Antiquities, this year an intensive and extensive operation of survey has been done in two of them, Zabara and Ibayd.¹⁴

They are close to each other: Zabara in the small Wadi Lasayfah, which leads into Wadi Ibayd, where Ibayd is located. There are 500 m of distance between them. In the case of Zabara, its coordinates are UTM 36N 673514E 2740262N. It is a large site divided into two parts: Middle and South Zabara. Middle Zabara is composed of several scattered structures, including tombs and small huts, together with a couple of large buildings.¹⁵

The success of the work is evident, as over 300 archaeological structures – buildings and tombs – have been documented. Particularly remarkable is one large building of rectangular shape and large perimeter walls, divided into several rooms and partially destroyed by

¹¹ Statistic presented here seems to show an extraordinarily high percentage of imported transport wares in the Early Roman context in the whole Eastern Desert. To compare, percentage of imported wares in Early Roman period from the last two seasons of excavations in Sikait equals 3.2 %, while in Berenike 8.73 %: Bartos, Geerts, Oleksiak 2024.

¹² The possible warehouse is located a few meters above the wadi, in the western slope of the surrounding hills.

¹³ The bridge was already mentioned previously by S.E. Sidebotham (Sidebotham et al. 2004, 25).

¹⁴ The survey was conducted by a team composed of J. Oller Guzmán, R. C. C. Geerts, R. Kolvers, and A. Puig Palerm. The suggested chronology of the site is based on the pottery study done by R.C.C. Geerts and is still preliminary.

¹⁵ Regarding the previous work conducted on Zabara, see Oller et al. 2022b, 73 n. 6.

erosion (Pl. XI 1). Complexity and dimensions of this edifice suggest that we are possibly dealing with one of the most important structures in Zabara. The massive perimeter walls – in some points 1.5 m of width by 1 m of preserved height –, the presence of one room protruding to the east from this perimetral wall – maybe a tower – and the intricacy of the built rooms may suggest a fort. According to the pottery, it may be related to the Ottoman period. Although this hypothesis can only be confirmed by excavation it is known that the mines were exploited during the Ottoman period and even F. Cailliaud mentions that some eighty years before his own arrival to Zabara Ali Bey al-Kabir had tried to reopen the mines. In this context, it is no wonder that a fort was established there to control the mining operations.¹⁶ Inside of the building, several circular structures maybe of funerary function related to the Bedouins of the area suggest a reuse of the locality after its abandonment.

Other interesting buildings can be found in this area of Middle Zabara, most of them having a circular shape and, in some cases, remarkable dimensions and features (Pl. XI 2). It is extremely complicated to determine their function without excavating them, but they suggest the existence of a complex settlement with a social and economic organization of the place. Again, Cailliaud already pointed out that aspect, stating even the presence of a mosque at the site.¹⁷ During the survey, we could not positively identify any mosque. However, some buildings had features, such as nicely built niches (Pl. XII 1), that may suggest a religious function.

In the case of South Zabara, different large buildings have been documented with an even more complicated organization. There, we have several complexes composed of different rooms of a broad range of dimensions which can be rectangular, circular or square in shape, in some cases including a central courtyard (Pl. XII 2). Ten complexes have been documented, together with different isolated structures, including several tombs. The dimensions of the larger complexes are between 300-350 m². The pottery points to an Early Islamic occupation (7th-10th c. AD) that may have been related to the emerald extracting operations that were conducted after the Islamic conquest of this region (Power 2012, 154-155). There are two major necropolises related to Zabara: the North necropolis and the South necropolis, with different types of tombs, among them typical tumuli graves, clusters of tumuli, or later individual inhumations marked by a headstone, the latest ones being related to the Islamic funerary ritual (Pl. XIII 1).

In the case of Ibayd, its coordinates are UTM 36N 673568E 2740939N. It is a smaller settlement, with some 50 buildings scattered along the northern part of the wadi (Pl. XIII 2). Chronologically it stretches from the Early Islamic to the Ottoman period. There are also

two necropolises – an East and a West necropolis – with similar types of graves as in Zabara.

At both sites, we recovered a large amount of material, mainly pottery, but also fragments of glass vessels, stone tools, bronze and iron items, and a couple of Islamic coins. Particularly interesting is a large amount of oil lamps, probably related to the main occupation of the inhabitants of both settlements: the extraction of emeralds. Regarding this subject, a detailed documentation of the emerald mines in this area has been conducted, identifying 124 underground exploitations distributed along an area of around 30 ha, which has been called SKMZ-U (Pl. XIV 1). This number confirms the Gebel Zabara area as one of the most significant emerald mining zones of the Eastern Desert and reinforces the importance of this activity, also after the end of Antiquity. We hope that this work will contribute to the knowledge and conservation of these unique sites.

In the Nugrus area, the survey documented an impressive building in the western part of the wadi (Pl. XIV 2).¹⁸ It comprises two rooms and is east-west orientated. The first room is 4.90 m long by 3.50 m wide, with the door in the northern side and five windows. The second room is 3 m long by 2.10 m wide and has five windows and five niches. Of these the one in the eastern wall, which is of triangular shape, may have been a small chapel. A small courtyard was added to the northern wall. The most striking aspect is that on the northern wall of the first room, several phrases were written in white painting (Pl. XV 2). Although these inscriptions are still under study, the preliminary results suggest that they are Coptic texts of sacred meaning.¹⁹ The ceramic material suggests a 5th - 6th c. AD chronology. The isolated position of the building, its chronology and dimensions, the possible presence of a chapel, the Coptic inscriptions, and, as we will see, the proximity of a necropolis with Christian tombs, suggest a Christian church. This option can only be confirmed by the excavation of the building.

From this building a pathway runs through the mountains in northwestern direction, leading to a previously unknown large necropolis. Composed of several clusters of tombs, it contains over 100 graves and many objects on the surface. The survey recovered pottery, fragments of glass, several decorated burners (Pl. XV 1), two fragments of terracotta figurines of horses – one of them with a Christian cross (Pl. XVI 1) –, and different amphorae with dipinti, one of them bearing the name Sekoit – or Sekoitos –,²⁰ perhaps related with the ancient name of the main settlement at Wadi Sikait (Pl. X 2). To differentiate this necropolis

18 This building was already documented by a team of the University of Bergen in the 1990s, although it has not been published anywhere as far as we know. We want to thank Dr. Julien Cooper for providing us with this information.

19 The study of the inscriptions is currently conducted by Dr. Leah Mascia.

20 We would like to express our gratitude to Dr. Rodney Ast for his valuable comments and suggestions concerning this dipinto.

16 Cailliaud 1821, 74.

17 Cailliaud 1821, 74.

from the previously known one which is located beside the main Nugrus site, we named it “South Necropolis” of Nugrus.

The documentation of both, the possible church and the necropolis, reinforces the importance of this area of Nugrus in the Late Antique period, giving evidence of an extended occupation deep into 6th c. AD, and offers the first clear evidence of Christian presence in the Smaragdos. Previously, only a small cross carved in the central altar of the Large Temple of Sikait and several small sites identified without certainty as Christian laura suggested Christian presence in this region.²¹ This additional evidence gives a new perspective, suggesting the existence of Christian communities in the area, although it is not possible to ascertain whether they were related to the emerald mining operations or to the monastic movement.

The conservation work

The final major goal of the season was the conservation work of structures and buildings within the Sikait settlement. This is one of the primary objectives of the mission, contributing to the preservation of the rich cultural heritage in the area. The conservation team focused on the reconstruction of some of the main buildings where excavation was carried out, the conservation of extracted materials from the excavation and the survey, and, finally, the analysis of the structural issues that affected the preservation of some of the main buildings in Sikait.

First, concerning the archaeological structures, the efforts focused on the so-called “Southern Temple”. There, work implied the recovery of some of the internal walls of the smaller room of the temple. The reconstruction was done without mortar, as it was in the original structure. However, the main building where conservation interventions were done was the so-called “Advanced Building”. There, a general cleaning of the standing walls was conducted, while a reconstruction of the missing parts of some of them was achieved to contribute to the stabilization of the entire structure. Also, in the upper part of some walls, a stone row was added to protect the original materials (Pl. XVI 2).

Regarding the archaeological artifacts, several conservation interventions were done in the most relevant pieces coming from different trenches and mines, including cleaning and stabilization operations on coins, stone and bronze figurines, ceramic ostraca, or organic materials such as baskets and ropes. All these interventions were conducted by a professional conservation team with extensive experience in working at Egyptian sites. The conservation criteria used were the following: minimal intervention and use of reversible and ecologically friendly materials.

Finally, we continued with the diagnostic study of two of the main structures of the site, the Southern Temple and the Large Temple, to analyze their actual state of conservation. To this end, plaster crack monitors were placed in the most compromised fissures to verify possible movements over the years. Also, among others petrographic studies were carried out, related to the hygrothermal properties of the rock or the bearing capacity of the complex. An endoscopic scanner was also used to reveal the discontinuities of forces on the bearing elements.

Conclusions

The 2024 archaeological season of the Sikait Project has continued to increase our knowledge about how the extraction and commercialization of green beryl worked in antiquity, basically in the Smaragdos region. As in previous years, the work was divided into different interventions. First, an intensive activity was done in Middle Sikait, with the survey of the area and the partial excavation of a building now known as the “Temple A”. The work conducted in this space confirmed its relevance during the Early Roman period, as it was probably one of the first exploited areas of the Smaragdos, with a direct link with the Roman army through the legio III Cyrenaica, maybe established in the area in a non-permanent seasonal camp. The excavation of the trench 025 also confirmed the importance of the religious aspect within the mining communities, with an important set of votive elements recovered from this “Temple A”.

The link with the Roman army, however, was especially detected in the so-called “SKMZ-G”. There, the detailed topographical survey and documentation of the mine SKPUS-229 allowed the recovery of two basket tags linked with the Cohors Nigri Camerensiana. This important discovery confirms the key role of the Roman army in the beginning of the mining operations at a large scale and reinforces the idea of an early start of the extraction under the Roman rule, probably under the reign of Augustus or Tiberius. Apart from the mines’s documentation, three new trenches were dug in this SKMZ-G, exploring different aspects related to the mining activity – trenches 022, 023, and 024.

A third area of work was the continuity of the survey of the Wadi el-Gemal National Park. In this regard, the survey of the Wadi Nugrus involved the documentation and discovery of extremely interesting elements such as a possible church and a new necropolis that supposes a breakthrough in our understanding of the Smaragdos, for instance, regarding the Christian presence there. Finally, a thorough survey was undertaken in two sites of the region that are severely endangered: Zabara and Ibayd, both from the Islamic period. The amazing results of this work, the documentation of over 300 archaeological features, allows for tracing the evolution of the Smaragdos after the end of Antiquity.

21 For the cross in the Large Temple, see Sidebotham et al. 2004, 21. Regarding the possible laura, see Sidebotham et al. 2002.

This last aspect, together with the continuation of the conservation work in Sikait, contribute to the main goal of the Sikait Project, which is, apart from the scientific discoveries, to contribute to the protection and preservation of the rich archaeological heritage of the Wadi el-Gemal National Park.

Bibliography

- Abdalla, H.M. – Saleh, G.M. 2021: The Pan-African Non-metallic Mineral Deposits of Egypt: Genetic and Exploration Constraints, in: Z. Hamimi, Z. – Arai, S. – Fowler, A.-R. – El-Bialy, M. Z. (eds.): *The Geology of the Egyptian Nubian Shield* (New York) 605-643.
- Abu El-Enen, M.M. – Abu-Alam, T.S. – Whitehouse, M.J. – Ali, K.A. – Okrusch, M. 2016: P-T path and timing of crustal thickening during amalgamation of East and West Gondwana: a case study from the Hafafit Metamorphic Complex, Eastern Desert of Egypt, *Lithos* 263, 213-238.
- Ali, M.A. – Abdel Gawad A.E. – Ghoneim, M.M. 2021: Geology and mineral chemistry of uranium- and thorium-bearing minerals in rare-metal (NYF) pegmatites of Um Solimate, South Eastern Desert, Egypt, *Acta Geologica Sinica* 95/5, 1568-1582.
- Bartos, N. – Geerts, R.C.A. – Oleksiak, J.M. (forthcoming): Crossroads of the Red Sea: New Ceramic Data from the Port of Berenike, in: Margariti, R. – Anastasopoulos, A. (eds.): *Red Sea Horizons, Edges and Transitions: Selected Papers of the Red Sea Project X* (Atlanta).
- Cailliaud, F. 1821 : *Voyage à l’Oasis de Thèbes et dans les déserts situés à l’Orient et à l’Occident de la Thébaïde* (Paris).
- Foster, B.C. – Rivard, J.-L. – Sidebotham, S.E. – Cuvigny, H. 2007: Survey of the emerald mines at Wadi Sikait. 2000/2001 seasons, in: Sidebotham, S.E. – Wendrich, W. (eds.): *Berenike 1999/2000. Report on the excavations at Berenike, including excavations in Wadi Kalalat and Siket, and the survey of the Mons Smaragdus region* (Los Angeles) 304-343.
- García-Dils, S. – Ast, R. – Oller, J. – Fernández, D. – Trevín, V. 2022: Loci and the legio III Cyrenaica in new inscriptions from the Roman emerald mines of Wadi Sikait (Eastern Desert of Egypt), *ZPE* 223, 109-119.
- García-Dils, S. – Oller, J. – Fernández, D. (forthcoming): Two basket tags from the Roman emerald mines of Wadi Sikait (Eastern Desert of Egypt), *ZPE*.
- García-Dils, S. – Oller, J. – Fernández, D. – Trevín, V. 2021: The emerald mines of Wadi Sikait (Egypt) from a diachronic perspective. Results of the 2020 and 2021 seasons of the Sikait Project, *TdE* 21, 19-48.
- Gilg, H.A. – Grundmann, G. 2022: The ancient emerald mines of Egypt, in: Giuliani, G. (ed.), *Émeraude – tout un monde!* (Saint-Julien-du-Pinet) 161-168.
- Grundmann, G. – Morteani, G. 2008: Multi-stage emerald formation during Pan-African regional metamorphism: The Zabara, Sikait, Umm Kabo deposits, South Eastern desert of Egypt, *Journal of African Earth Sciences* 50, 168-187.
- Harrell, J.A. 2004: Archaeological geology of the world’s first emerald mines, *Geoscience Canada* 31/2, 69-76.
- Harrell J.A. 2006: Archaeological geology of Wadi Sikait, *PalArch’s Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology* 4/1, 1-12.
- Harrell, J.A. 2019: Geology, in: Sidebotham, S.E. – Gates-Foster, J. – Rivard, J.L. (eds.), *The Archaeological Survey of the Desert Roads Between Berenike and the Nile Valley: Expeditions by the University of Michigan and the University of Delaware to the Eastern Desert of Egypt, 1987-2015* (Boston) 51-72.
- Harrell, J.A. 2024: *Archaeology and geology of Ancient Egyptian stones* (Oxford).
- Hassan, M.A. – El-Shatoury, H.M. 1976: Beryl Occurrences in Egypt, *Mining Geology* 26, 253-262.
- Oller, J. 2022: Las esmeraldas en las fuentes literarias clásicas: una breve aproximación. *Espacio, Tiempo y Forma, Historia Antigua* 35, 77-110.
- Oller, J. – Fernández, D. – Trevín, V. – Achon, O. 2019: La explotación de esmeraldas en el Egipto romano. Primeros resultados del Sikait Project, *Trabajos de Egiptología* 10, 283-303.
- Oller, J. – Fernández, D. – Trevín, V. – Achon, O. – García-Dils, S. 2021a: New evidence regarding emerald production in Roman Egypt at Wadi Sikait (Eastern Desert), *JNES* 80/1, 123-142.
- Oller, J. – Fernández, D. – Trevín, V. – Achon, O. – García-Dils, S. – Sánchez, F. 2021b: Emerald Mining during the Roman Period in the Egyptian Eastern Desert: Recent Evidence from Wadi Sikait, *Thetis* 26, 25-35.
- Oller, J. – García-Dils, S. – Fernández, D. – Carrasco López, J.M. – Gilg, H.A. – Eguiluz, D. – Molina, A. – Martín, E. 2022a: Results of the 2022 Season in the Beryl Mining Area of Wadi Sikait: Excavations in Sikait and Documentation of the Emerald Mines, *Thetis* 27, 7-12.
- Oller, J. – García-Dils, S. – Fernández, D. – Ozcoz, P. – Oleksiak, J. – Eguiluz, D. – Molina, A. – Burgaya, B. – Sagristà, L. – Salvia, S. – Carrasco, J.M. 2023: The 2023 Archaeological Season in the Emerald Mines of Wadi Sikait: Excavation in Sikait, Documentation of the Mining Regions, and Survey of the Wadi el Gemal National Park, *Thetis* 28, 17-22.
- Oller, J. – Trevín, V. – Fernández, D. – Oleksiak, J. – Sidebotham, S.E. 2022b: A new enigmatic settlement discovered in the Eastern Desert of Egypt: Zabara Northwest, *REA*, 124/1, 71-91.
- Power, T. 2012: *The Red Sea from Byzantium to the Caliphate, AD 500-1000* (Cairo).
- Rivard, J.-L. – Foster, B.C. – Sidebotham, S.E. 2002: Emerald city, *Archaeology* 55, 36-41.

- Shaw, I. – Bunbury, J. – Jameson, R. 1999: Emerald mining in Roman and Byzantine Egypt, *JRA* 12, 203-215.
- Sidebotham, S.E. 2011: *Berenike and the ancient maritime spice route* (Los Angeles).
- Sidebotham, S.E. – Barnard, H. – Pyke, G. 2002: Five Enigmatic Late Roman Settlements in the Eastern Desert, *JEA* 88, 187-225.
- Sidebotham, S.E. – Gates-Foster, J. – Rivard, J.-L. (eds.) 2019: *The archaeological survey of the desert roads between Berenike and the Nile valley. Expeditions by the University of Michigan and the University of Delaware to the Eastern Desert of Egypt, 1987-2015* (Boston).
- Sidebotham, S.E. – Hense, M. – Nouwens, M. 2008: *The Red Land. The illustrated archaeology of Egypt's Eastern Desert* (Cairo-New York).
- Sidebotham, S.E. – Nouwens, H.M. – Hense, A.M. – Harrell, J.A. 2004: Preliminary report on archaeological fieldwork at Sikait (Eastern Desert, Egypt), and environs: 2002-2003, *Sahara* 15, 7-30.
- Soukiassian, G. 1983: Les autels 'à cornes' ou 'à acrotères' en Égypte, *BIFAO* 83, 317-333.
- Thomas, R. – Masson, A. 2015: Altars, sundials, minor architectural objects and models, in: Villing, A. – Bergeron, M. – Bourogiannis, G. – Johnston, A. – Leclère, F. – Masson, A. – Ross, T. (eds.). *Naukratis: Greeks in Egypt* (London), 2-14.
- Zaki Khedr, M – Saleh, G.M. – Abdelfadil, K.M. – Takazwa, E. – Abdelra man, K. – Tamur, A. – AlEl-Shafei, S. 2024: The geology and mineral chemistry of beryl mineralization, South Eastern Desert, Egypt: A deeper insight into genesis and distribution, *Minerals* 14-465, <https://doi.org/10.3390/min14050465>.

1: Location of the Wadi el-Gemal National Park in Egypt

2: Map of the Smaragdus with the main documented sites

Map of Wadi Sikait's mining areas, with Middle Sikait circled in white

1: View from the west of the Middle Sikait area, specifically the base of the wadi where the intensive survey was conducted

2: Area of Middle Sikait, with the mines and the three buildings at the center of the image

1: View from the south of the so-called "Temple A" of Middle Sikait prior to its excavation

2: Detail of the Harpocrates medallion

3: Drawing and photograph of the Sothic dog found in trench 025 (drawing and photograph by Maria Lausz).

1: View of the second room at Middle Sikait after its excavation, with the two votive pits, in the center and in the upper left corner of the image

2: Drawing and photograph of the horned altar recovered in the Temple A (drawing and photograph by Maria Lausz)

1: Detail of the copper alloy plaque in the second room at the moment of finding

2: View from the west of the possible altar located in front of "Temple A"

1: View from the south of the trench 025 after its excavation

2: Documentation of the Underground Complex SKPUS-229-230-231-232-426

1: The two basket tags found in the Underground Complex SKPUS-229-230-231-232-426

2: Trench 022: sorting area linked to the mine SKPUS-229

1: Image of trench 023 after finishing its excavation

2: Detail of a textile fragment found in trench 023

1: Detail of the entrance to the storage space – trench 024

2: Dipinto with the name "Sekoit"

3: View from the south of the bridge in Wadi Umm Selimate

1: View from the east of the possible fort in Middle Zabara. In the central and right part of the image we can see the best-preserved part of the perimeter wall – including the north-east corner and the protruding room. In the upper part of the image, the destruction caused by the wadi can be appreciated – separating the main part of this structure from the possible western perimeter wall

2: View from the north of one of the main circular buildings in Middle Zabara

1: Detail of one of the niches in one of the buildings of Middle Zabara

2: View from the west of some of the Early Islamic buildings in South Zabara

1: View from the west of the Islamic East Necropolis from Zabara

2: One of the buildings documented in Ibayd

1: View from the east of the west mining area, with the large concentration of mining debris coming from the emerald mines

2: The building documented in the Nugrus area

1: Drawing and photograph of the burner found in the necropolis of Nugrus (drawing and photograph by Maria Lausz)

2: Detail of part of the Coptic inscription

1: Drawing and photograph of the fragment of horse figurine – the neck– with a Christian cross on it (drawing and photograph by Maria Lausz)

2: Detail of the “Advanced Building” after the conservation intervention